

1 **Supporting Information**

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3 Article title: Multifunctionality debt in global drylands linked to past biome and
4 climate

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9 The following Supporting Information is available for this article:

10

12 **Figure S1** Correlations (Pearson's r) between the multifunctionality index (mean
13 Z-score of 12 functions) and the 12 individual ecosystem functions used to build it.
14 ORC, soil organic carbon; iNDVI, annual integral of normalized difference vegetation
15 index; PEN, soil pentoses; HEX, soil hexoses; NIT, soil nitrate; DON, soil dissolved
16 organic nitrogen; PRO, soil proteins; NTR, soil potential nitrogen transformation rate;
17 AVP, soil available inorganic phosphorus; FOS, soil enzymatic activity of phosphatase;
18 TP, soil total phosphorus; IOP, soil inorganic phosphorus.

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21 **Figure S2** Correlation between our multifunctionality index (mean Z-score of 12
 22 functions) and that calculated as the mean Z-score of 16 ecosystem functions used in
 23 previous studies (Gross et al., 2017; Maestre et al., 2012): soil nitrate and ammonium
 24 availabilities, total nitrogen, organic carbon, amino acids, proteins, pentoses, hexoses,
 25 aromatic compounds, phenols, potential nitrogen depolymerization and potential
 26 nitrogen mineralization, available inorganic phosphorus, soil enzymatic activities of
 27 phosphatase and β -glucosidase and plant productivity.

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30 **Figure S3** Correlation between annual integral normalized difference vegetation
31 index (iNDVI) averaged for the periods 2000 to 2013 and average NDVI of the
32 images before, during and after each soil and vegetation survey.

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36 **Figure S4.** Semivariogram of the residuals from a generalized least squares (gls)
 37 fitted model of multifunctionality and predictor variables. **(a)** Residuals of a fitted
 38 model that does not account for potential spatial autocorrelation. The blue line shows
 39 an exponential fitting between the semivariance and distance ($P = 0.026$). **(b)**
 40 Residuals of a gls fitted model that account for potential spatial autocorrelation. We
 41 did not find any significant fitting between the semivariance and distance, suggesting
 42 that our analyses effectively removed the spatial autocorrelation.

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44 **Figure S5** *A priori* confirmatory path analysis evaluating the direct and indirect

45 effects of climate and biome legacies on multifunctionality.

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Figure S6 Semivariogram of the residuals of soil sand content from a confirmatory path analysis (CPA). **(a)** Residuals of CPA that does not account for potential spatial autocorrelation. The blue line shows an exponential fitting between the semivariance and distance ($P = 0.017$). **(b)** Residuals of CPA that account for potential spatial autocorrelation. The exponential spatial autocorrelation structure no longer exists, suggesting that this analysis effectively removed the spatial autocorrelation. Semivariogram of the residuals of multifunctionality from a CPA is similar to that shown in Figure S4.

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59 **Figure S7** Quadratic relationship between multifunctionality and soil pH and site
60 elevation.

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63 **Figure S8** Confirmatory path analysis (CPA) accounting for the direct and indirect
 64 effects of environmental predictors on ecosystem multifunctionality (calculated as the
 65 mean Z-score of 12 functions, see Materials and Methods section in the main text) of
 66 a subset of 123 drylands that have plant functional traits available. The significant
 67 path coefficients, describing the strength and sign of the relationships among the
 68 variables, were shown adjacent to the arrows (significance codes: *** $P < 0.001$, ** P
 69 < 0.01 , * $P < 0.05$). MAT: Mean annual temperature; MAP: Mean annual
 70 precipitation; pH: soil pH; Sand: soil sand content. Plant traits include SkewH, the
 71 skewness of abundance distributions for plant heights, and KurtSLA, the kurtosis of
 72 abundance distributions for specific leaf area (Gross *et al.*, 2017). Fisher's $C = 37.09$
 73 with P -value = 0.51 and on 38 degrees of freedom.

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76 **Figure S9** Confirmatory path analysis (CPA) accounting for the direct and indirect
 77 effects of environmental predictors on ecosystem multifunctionality (calculated as the
 78 mean Z-score of 12 functions), after accounting for human influence. We calculated
 79 the residuals after fitting ecosystem multifunctionality vs. human influence and
 80 used the residuals as the final multifunctionality in CPA. The human influence index
 81 was obtained from the Last of the Wild Project, Version 2 (Last of the Wild Data,
 82 2005). This is a global dataset of 1-kilometer resolution, created from nine global data
 83 layers covering human population pressure (population density), human land use and
 84 infrastructure (built-up areas, nighttime lights, land use/land cover), and human access
 85 (coastlines, roads, railroads, navigable rivers). The significant path coefficients,
 86 describing the strength and sign of the relationships among the variables, are shown
 87 adjacent to the arrows (significance levels as follows: $*** P < 0.001$, $** P < 0.01$, $*P$
 88 < 0.05). MAT: mean annual temperature; MAP: annual precipitation; Soil sand: soil
 89 sand content. The confirmatory path analysis had a Fisher's C = 5.47 with P -value =
 90 0.49 and on 6 degrees of freedom.

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94 **Figure S10** Confirmatory path analysis (CPA) accounting for the direct and indirect
 95 effects of environmental predictors on ecosystem multifunctionality calculated as the
 96 mean Z-score of 16 functions used in previous studies (Gross et al., 2017; Maestre et
 97 al., 2012). The 16 functions included soil nitrate and ammonium availabilities, total
 98 nitrogen, organic carbon, amino acids, proteins, pentoses, hexoses, aromatic
 99 compounds, phenols, potential nitrogen depolymerization and potential nitrogen
 100 mineralization, available inorganic phosphorus, soil enzymatic activities of
 101 phosphatase and β -glucosidase and plant productivity. Fisher's C = 24.61 with *P*-value
 102 = 0.32 and on 22 degrees of freedom.

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105 **Methods S1** Laboratory measurement of soil related ecosystem functions

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107 Soil organic carbon (C) was measured by colorimetry after oxidation with a mixture
108 of potassium dichromate and sulfuric acid (Anderson, & Ingram, 1987). Soil pentoses
109 and hexoses were measured colorimetrically from soil extracts as described in
110 Delgado-Baquerizo et al. (2015). Soil samples (2.5 g of soil) were extracted with 0.5
111 M K₂SO₄ in a ratio 1:5. Extracts were shaken in an orbital shaker at 200 r.p.m. for 1 h
112 at 20°C and filtered to pass a 0.45-µm Millipore filter (Jones, & Willett, 2006). Soil
113 aromatic compounds were measured according to Gregorich & Carter (2007). The
114 activity of β-glucosidase was measured by determination of the amount of
115 p-nitrophenol released from 0.5 g soil after incubation at 37°C for 1 h with the
116 substrate p-nitrophenyl-β-D-glucopyranoside in trishydroxymethyl aminomethane
117 buffer (Tabatabai, 1982).

118 Soil ammonium and nitrate were measured colorimetrically from soil extracts.
119 Total nitrogen (N) was determined using a CN analyzer (Leco CHN628 Series; Leco
120 Corporation, St. Joseph, Michigan, USA). Soil dissolved organic N concentration was
121 determined as the difference between total N and inorganic N (Delgado-Baquerizo,
122 Covelo, & Gallardo, 2011). Soil proteins and amino acids were measured according to
123 Gregorich & Carter (2007). Soil potential N depolymerization and potential
124 mineralization were measured by determination of dissolved organic N and mineral N
125 before and after incubation in the laboratory at 80% of water holding capacity and
126 30°C for 14 days, respectively (Allen, 1986; i.e., reductions in biodiversity associated
127 to past legacies could negatively influence current and future ecosystem functions;
128 Isbell, Tilman, Polasky, & Loreau, 2015).

129 Soil total phosphorus (P) was measured using a Skalar San11 Analyzer after
130 digestion with sulphuric acid. Available phosphorus was determined colorimetrically
131 from sodium bicarbonate extracts (Tiessen, & Moir, 2007). Soil inorganic P was
132 measured following the soil-P fractionation protocol of Tiessen & Moir (2007).
133 Phosphatase activity was measured by determination of the amount of p-nitrophenol
134 released from 0.5 g soil after incubation at 37°C for 1 h with the substrate
135 p-nitrophenyl phosphate in MUB buffer (Tabatabai, & Bremner, 1969).

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137 **Table S1** Current (Olson *et al.*, 2001) and Last Glacial Maximum (LGM; Ray, &
138 Adams, 2001) distributions of biomes for the 236 drylands studied. 1, tropical and
139 subtropical moist broadleaf forests; 2, tropical and subtropical dry broadleaf forests; 3,
140 tropical and subtropical coniferous forests; 4, temperate broadleaf and mixed forests;
141 5, temperate conifer forests; 6, boreal forests/taiga; 7, tropical and subtropical
142 grasslands, savannas and shrublands; 8, temperate grasslands, savannas and
143 shrublands; 9, flooded grasslands and savannas; 10, montane grasslands and
144 shrublands; 11, tundra; 12, Mediterranean forests, woodlands and scrub; 13, deserts
145 and xeric shrublands; 14, mangroves; 15, not vegetated (lake, open water, and ice).

Site ID	Country	Latitude	Longitude	Current biome	LGM biome
1	Argentina	-41.8078	-69.6764	8	13
2	Argentina	-41.2379	-70.4239	8	13
3	Argentina	-41.1067	-70.8911	8	8
4	Argentina	-41.0043	-71.0595	8	8
5	Argentina	-41.2533	-70.0809	8	13
6	Argentina	-41.0335	-70.5245	8	13
7	Argentina	-38.9909	-63.9338	8	13
8	Argentina	-38.8396	-64.4952	8	13
9	Argentina	-38.764	-65.0733	8	13
10	Argentina	-38.7005	-66.1831	8	13
11	Argentina	-37.6714	-67.2332	8	13
12	Argentina	-37.55	-68.05	8	10
13	Argentina	-31.5511	-67.425	8	13
14	Argentina	-31.356	-66.8201	7	13
15	Argentina	-31.4883	-67.2812	7	13
16	Argentina	-31.7044	-68.1523	8	10
17	Argentina	-31.3908	-66.9702	7	13
18	Argentina	-31.7189	-67.8373	8	10
19	Australia	-34.2235	142.5501	12	13
20	Australia	-34.2043	142.5569	12	13
21	Australia	-34.2478	142.4817	12	13
22	Australia	-34.0185	142.5088	12	13
23	Australia	-34.1094	142.5436	12	13

24	Australia	-34.1992	142.418	12	13
25	Australia	-33.9602	142.4601	12	13
26	Australia	-33.9705	142.6647	12	13
27	Australia	-34.106	142.5681	12	13
28	Australia	-33.9639	142.4618	12	13
29	Australia	-33.9311	142.6862	12	13
30	Australia	-33.944	142.6674	12	13
31	Australia	-32.1611	145.8944	8	13
32	Australia	-31.5561	146.3097	8	13
33	Australia	-31.317	146.8961	8	13
34	Australia	-31.3009	146.906	8	13
35	Australia	-31.8575	147.7078	8	2
36	Australia	-32.1167	146.6639	8	13
37	Brasil	-11.339	-41.2441	13	13
38	Brasil	-11.3388	-41.2438	13	13
39	Brasil	-9.73167	-38.6831	13	13
40	Brasil	-9.73139	-38.6836	13	13
41	Brasil	-11.1177	-42.7368	13	7
42	Brasil	-11.1253	-42.7371	13	7
43	Chile	-32.4631	-71.2336	12	8
44	Chile	-33.27	-70.9031	4	8
45	Chile	-33.1192	-71.3639	12	8
46	Chile	-32.4856	-71.3703	12	8
47	Chile	-34.1072	-71.3458	12	8
48	Chile	-34.1074	-71.3452	12	8
49	Chile	-29.3114	-71.2449	12	13
50	Chile	-29.311	-71.2469	12	13
51	Chile	-29.3109	-71.2473	12	13
52	Chile	-29.7502	-71.2512	12	13
53	Chile	-29.7499	-71.2507	12	13
54	Chile	-29.7499	-71.2502	12	13
55	Chile	-30.6623	-71.6636	12	8
56	Chile	-30.6609	-71.6642	12	8

57	Chile	-30.6625	-71.6636	12	8
58	Chile	-31.2002	-71.5847	12	8
59	Chile	-31.2001	-71.5849	12	8
60	Chile	-31.1998	-71.5854	12	8
61	China	49.26269	119.1774	8	11
62	China	49.49433	118.4038	8	11
63	China	49.52533	117.2721	8	11
64	China	49.03153	116.9945	8	11
65	China	48.60978	116.7866	8	11
66	China	48.22308	116.0158	8	11
67	Ecuador	-3.97516	-79.4285	1	13
68	Ecuador	-3.97457	-79.4285	1	13
69	Ecuador	-3.99078	-79.4248	1	13
70	Ecuador	-3.99046	-79.4244	1	13
71	Ecuador	-3.99631	-79.4298	1	13
72	Ecuador	-3.99644	-79.4272	1	13
73	Ecuador	-3.99644	-79.4419	1	13
74	Ecuador	-3.99605	-79.4411	1	13
75	Ecuador	-4.00429	-79.4975	1	13
76	Ecuador	-3.99865	-79.4973	1	13
77	Ecuador	-4.00423	-79.4944	1	13
78	Ecuador	-4.00438	-79.4953	1	13
79	Ecuador	-4.01259	-79.4854	1	13
80	Ecuador	-4.01323	-79.4859	1	13
81	Ecuador	-4.01593	-79.4778	1	13
82	Ecuador	-4.01606	-79.478	1	13
83	Iran	36.69617	58.6695	13	13
84	Iran	37.37111	56.56094	5	13
85	Iran	37.42908	58.10956	13	13
86	Israel	31.35774	34.82106	13	13
87	Israel	31.3577	34.82171	13	13
88	Israel	31.35774	34.82208	13	13
89	Israel	31.35781	34.82223	13	13

90	Israel	31.35786	34.82251	13	13
91	Israel	31.35779	34.82087	13	13
92	Israel	31.27118	34.65224	13	13
93	Israel	31.27095	34.65205	13	13
94	Israel	31.27077	34.6519	13	13
95	Israel	31.27072	34.65223	13	13
96	Israel	31.27093	34.6524	13	13
97	Israel	31.27108	34.65253	13	13
98	Kenya	0.352	36.89439	7	7
99	Kenya	0.575333	37.53017	7	7
100	Mexico	22.24653	-99.6556	13	2
101	Mexico	23.60169	-100.944	13	2
102	Mexico	22.64451	-100.421	3	2
103	Mexico	22.64831	-99.8946	13	2
104	Mexico	23.25488	-101.055	13	2
105	Mexico	23.2047	-101.274	13	2
106	Mexico	23.738	-101.249	13	2
107	Mexico	22.35093	-102.455	13	2
108	Mexico	22.35244	-102.456	13	2
109	Mexico	21.76967	-101.674	3	2
110	Mexico	21.7718	-101.674	3	2
111	Morocco	33.05249	-2.42259	12	13
112	Morocco	34.15918	-2.3729	12	13
113	Morocco	34.43087	-2.1926	12	13
114	Morocco	33.97657	-3.3735	12	13
115	Morocco	34.47305	-3.63886	12	13
116	Morocco	34.44201	-3.59251	12	13
117	Morocco	34.30967	-1.9993	12	13
118	Morocco	33.87247	-3.63389	12	13
119	Morocco	33.93262	-3.55875	12	13
120	Morocco	33.06768	-2.72871	12	13
121	Morocco	34.63322	-3.41363	12	13
122	Morocco	34.62555	-3.46492	12	13

123	Peru	-16.1898	-71.3571	13	15
124	Peru	-16.2156	-71.3598	13	15
125	Peru	-16.2104	-71.4338	13	15
126	Peru	-16.1752	-71.4409	13	15
127	Peru	-16.1819	-71.4775	13	15
128	Peru	-16.2666	-71.3849	13	11
129	Peru	-16.0521	-71.4159	13	15
130	Peru	-16.3812	-71.2309	10	15
131	Peru	-16.3624	-71.2838	10	15
132	Peru	-16.3551	-70.9436	10	15
133	Peru	-16.4343	-71.014	10	15
134	Spain	39.04854	-2.23043	12	8
135	Spain	39.04821	-2.2306	12	8
136	Spain	40.32674	-3.42392	12	8
137	Spain	40.31999	-3.42684	12	8
138	Spain	40.24831	-3.25657	12	8
139	Spain	37.79923	-1.30383	12	8
140	Spain	37.80032	-1.30543	12	8
141	Spain	40.27333	-3.51348	12	8
142	Spain	40.27382	-3.51245	12	8
143	Spain	40.14332	-3.13294	12	8
144	Spain	40.07361	-2.89909	12	11
145	Spain	40.06823	-2.90073	12	11
146	Spain	40.20884	-3.41819	12	8
147	Spain	40.20878	-3.41916	12	8
148	Spain	39.99258	-3.62254	12	8
149	Spain	39.99204	-3.61895	12	8
150	Spain	39.99046	-3.6231	12	8
151	Spain	37.82164	-1.67229	12	8
152	Spain	37.82116	-1.67375	12	8
153	Spain	40.1861	-3.50346	12	8
154	Spain	40.18601	-3.50287	12	8
155	Spain	40.0414	-3.21162	12	8

156	Spain	39.20878	-2.51409	12	8
157	Spain	39.20754	-2.51477	12	8
158	Spain	38.58822	-1.20378	12	8
159	Spain	38.58861	-1.19948	12	8
160	Spain	40.35465	-2.87835	12	11
161	Spain	40.35479	-2.87744	12	11
162	Spain	38.79186	-1.7177	12	11
163	Spain	39.87741	-2.78807	12	11
164	Spain	38.31026	-0.75507	12	8
165	Spain	39.03824	-2.25791	12	8
166	Spain	39.00995	-2.66289	12	11
167	Spain	38.16509	-1.50899	12	8
168	Spain	37.72133	-1.83699	12	8
169	Spain	40.1583	-2.8891	12	11
170	Spain	37.92318	-1.47017	12	8
171	Spain	37.72673	-1.7846	12	8
172	Spain	38.30858	-0.96325	12	8
173	Spain	40.36936	-3.38868	12	8
174	Spain	37.59307	-1.23238	12	8
175	Spain	39.53867	-1.80229	12	11
176	Spain	38.06553	-1.52704	12	8
177	Spain	39.12751	-2.34514	12	8
178	Spain	38.76528	-1.02017	12	8
179	Spain	39.00149	-2.83814	12	8
180	Spain	39.05299	-2.57225	12	11
181	Spain	40.01803	-2.87935	12	11
182	Spain	40.26021	-3.48551	12	8
183	Spain	37.6339	-2.03961	12	11
184	Spain	40.11212	-3.46299	12	8
185	Spain	39.86184	-2.54375	12	11
186	Spain	37.89236	-1.70319	12	8
187	Tunisia	34.49425	9.647121	12	13
188	Tunisia	35.16777	8.673783	12	13

189	Tunisia	33.52157	9.97436	12	13
190	Tunisia	35.16004	9.116646	12	13
191	Tunisia	34.95645	9.717897	12	13
192	Tunisia	32.98347	10.4986	12	13
193	Tunisia	34.68631	10.5084	12	13
194	Tunisia	33.76211	10.02649	12	13
195	Tunisia	35.63419	9.687825	12	13
196	Tunisia	35.85542	9.7735	12	13
197	USA	37.11345	-112.552	13	10
198	USA	38.17351	-109.71	13	10
199	USA	37.58193	-109.91	13	10
200	USA	37.08609	-111.697	13	10
201	USA	37.25973	-109.927	13	10
202	USA	37.85157	-111.313	13	10
203	USA	37.50728	-112.022	13	10
204	USA	37.73041	-109.414	13	10
205	USA	38.00311	-110.517	13	10
206	USA	36.68547	-111.857	13	10
207	USA	33.74714	-115.808	13	12
208	USA	33.74776	-115.81	13	12
209	USA	33.75426	-115.796	13	12
210	USA	33.7495	-115.806	13	12
211	USA	33.75067	-115.812	13	12
212	USA	33.75361	-115.796	13	12
213	Venezuela	9.666772	-69.9467	13	7
214	Venezuela	9.666497	-69.9469	13	7
215	Venezuela	10.00232	-69.6482	13	7
216	Venezuela	10.00236	-69.6481	13	7
217	Venezuela	9.767697	-69.8209	13	7
218	Venezuela	9.767953	-69.8208	13	7
219	Venezuela	8.430611	-65.4032	7	7
220	Venezuela	8.427306	-65.4055	7	7
221	Venezuela	7.945083	-64.7168	7	7

222	Venezuela	7.946222	-64.7172	7	7
223	Venezuela	8.321472	-65.1877	7	7
224	Venezuela	8.321611	-65.1887	7	7
225	Botswana	-26.7759	20.84419	13	13
226	Botswana	-26.7863	21.31281	13	13
227	Botswana	-26.3967	22.08183	13	13
228	Botswana	-26.2597	22.18836	13	13
229	Botswana	-25.9374	22.42057	13	13
230	Botswana	-25.2001	22.93104	13	13
231	Ghana	9.425314	-1.05555	7	13
232	Ghana	9.379794	-0.66357	7	13
233	Ghana	10.65118	-0.84634	7	13
234	Ghana	10.86392	-0.6689	7	13
235	Burkina Faso	12.28289	-1.46284	7	13
236	Burkina Faso	12.52043	-1.37231	7	13

147 **Table S2** Correlations (Pearson's) among the 12 ecosystem functions used to calculate multifunctionality. ORC, soil organic carbon; PEN, soil
 148 pentoses; iNDVI, annual integral of normalized difference vegetation index; HEX, soil hexoses; NIT, soil nitrate; DON, soil dissolved organic
 149 nitrogen; PRO, soil proteins; NTR, soil potential nitrogen transformation rate; AVP, soil available inorganic phosphorus; FOS, soil enzymatic
 150 activity of phosphatase; TP, soil total phosphorus; IOP, soil inorganic phosphorus.

	ORC	iNDVI	PEN	HEX	NIT	DON	PRO	NTR	AVP	FOS	TP
iNDVI	0.5										
PEN	0.24	0.04									
HEX	0.56	0.44	-0.06								
NIT	0.11	-0.02	0.05	0.13							
DON	0.13	0.24	-0.1	0.35	0.11						
PRO	0.45	0.04	0.18	0.44	0.25	0.14					
NTR	0.5	0.11	0.13	0.36	0.26	-0.15	0.44				
AVP	-0.12	-0.12	-0.15	0.07	0.1	0.18	0.17	-0.02			
FOS	0.52	0.43	-0.12	0.51	0.02	0.1	0.07	0.39	0.03		
TP	0.14	-0.14	-0.05	0.22	0.29	0.15	0.19	0.15	0.41	0.13	
IOP	-0.34	-0.35	-0.05	-0.26	-0.06	0.01	-0.07	-0.21	0.25	-0.25	0.26

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152 **REFERENCES**

- 153 Allen, S. E. (1986). Chemical analysis. *Methods in plant ecology*, 285-344
- 154 Anderson, J. & Ingram, J. (1987). Tropical soil biology and fertility methods
155 handbook. *Aberystwith, UNESCO/IUBS*,
- 156 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Covelo, F. & Gallardo, A. (2011). Dissolved Organic
157 Nitrogen in Mediterranean Ecosystems. *Pedosphere*, 21, 309-318.
158 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160\(11\)60131-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1002-0160(11)60131-8)
- 159 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., García-Palacios, P., Milla, R., Gallardo, A. & Maestre, F. T.
160 (2015). Soil characteristics determine soil carbon and nitrogen availability
161 during leaf litter decomposition regardless of litter quality. *Soil Biology and*
162 *Biochemistry*, 81, 134-142
- 163 Gregorich, E. G. & Carter, M. R. (2007). *Soil sampling and methods of analysis*, CRC
164 Press.
- 165 Gross, N., Bagousse-Pinguet, Y. L., Liancourt, P., Berdugo, M., Gotelli, N. J. &
166 Maestre, F. T. (2017). Functional trait diversity maximizes ecosystem
167 multifunctionality. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1, 0132.
168 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0132>
- 169 Isbell, F., Tilman, D., Polasky, S. & Loreau, M. (2015). The biodiversity-dependent
170 ecosystem service debt. *Ecology Letters*, 18, 119-134.
171 <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12393>
- 172 Jones, D. & Willett, V. (2006). Experimental evaluation of methods to quantify
173 dissolved organic nitrogen (DON) and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) in soil.
174 *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 38, 991-999
- 175 Last of the Wild Data (2005). *Wildlife Conservation Society - WCS, Center for*
176 *International Earth Science Information Network - CIESIN - Columbia*
177 *University, Last of the Wild Project, Version 2, 2005 (LWP-2): Global Human*
178 *Influence Index (HII) Dataset (Geographic)*. Palisades, NY, NASA
179 Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC).
- 180 Maestre, F. T., Quero, J. L., Gotelli, N. J., Escudero, A., Ochoa, V.,
181 Delgado-Baquerizo, M., . . . Zaady, E. (2012). Plant Species Richness and
182 Ecosystem Multifunctionality in Global Drylands. *Science*, 335, 214-218.
183 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1215442>
- 184 Olson, D. M., Dinerstein, E., Wikramanayake, E. D., Burgess, N. D., Powell, G. V. N.,
185 Underwood, E. C., . . . Kassem, K. R. (2001). Terrestrial Ecoregions of the

186 World: A New Map of Life on Earth. *BioScience*, 51, 933-938.
187 [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2001\)051\[0933:teotwa\]2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2001)051[0933:teotwa]2.0.co;2)
188 Ray, N. & Adams, J. (2001). A GIS-based vegetation map of the world at the Last
189 Glacial Maximum (25,000-15,000 BP). *Internet Archaeology*, 11.
190 <https://doi.org/10.11141/ia.11.2>
191 Tabatabai, M. (1982). Methods of soil analyses part 2. *American Society of Agronomy*,
192 *Madison*,
193 Tabatabai, M. & Bremner, J. (1969). Use of p-nitrophenyl phosphate for assay of soil
194 phosphatase activity. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 1, 301-307
195 Tiessen, H. & Moir, J. (2007) Characterisation of Available P by Sequential
196 Extraction in Soil Sampling and Methods of Analysis. Carter, MR ed.
197
198